

Trends in spectral parameters and nephelauxetic ratio values for some lanthanoid(III)-catechol complexes

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Electronic spectral studies of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Er^{III} in complexation with catechol (cat) have been undertaken with a view to evaluate the oscillator strengths (f_{JO}), Judd-Ofelt parameters (τ_λ), inter-electronic repulsion Racah parameters (δE^K) and nephelauxetic ratios ($\delta E^3/\delta E^1$) in the pH range 4.0–6.0. The extent of covalency in metal-ligand interaction have been estimated. The oscillator strength values for some specific hypersensitive transitions were found to be significantly large.

In continuation with our earlier studies on the electronic spectra of lanthanum(III) metal ions in different environments¹, the present work was undertaken with a view to study the trends in spectral parameters and nephelauxetic ratio values for Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Er^{III} in complexation with catechol.

Results and Discussion

The data in Table 1 show that the oscillator strength values (f_{JO}) attain a maximum at pH 5.5, which is the pH of maximum complexation. A pH profile of the oscillator strength values (figure omitted for simplicity) exhibited a maximum at pH 5.5–6.0. Deviations beyond pH 6.5–7.0 may be on account of formation of hydroxo complexes. Table 2 records the f_{JO} values for [Pr^{III}/Nd^{III}/Er^{III}-cat] at pH 5.5 in the range of maximum complexation. Separate studies on determination of concentration of [Ln(III)-cat] species at different pH values using SGOGS-NR computer software² show (figure omitted for brevity) good agreement with the above observation. The [Ln(III)-cat] concentrations were determined using the $\log K_n^H$ values for cat, the pK_w for water and the appropriate $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{ML(OH)}^M$ values for the corresponding binary [ML] and hydroxo-complexes [MLOH]. An increase in the degree of complexation may also be visualized by the variations in the ${}^2P_{1/2}$ assignments for Nd^{III}. The ${}^2P_{1/2}$ assignment sensitive to the M-L interactions and the Ln(III) donor atom bond distance³ show a decrease in the energy [viz. pH 2.04, E 23543; pH 4.0, E 23501; pH 5.0, E 23407; pH 5.5, E 23377; pH 6.0, E (cm⁻¹) 23488] with increased pH values, indicating greater release of inter-electronic repulsion with increased degree of complexation.

Table 1. Representative f_{JO} values for [Pr^{III}-cat] complexes at different pH values

pH	$f_{JO} (\times 10^4)$ for			
	1D_2	3P_0	${}^3P_1; {}^1I_6$	3P_2
	16850	20800	21400–21700	22600
	E (cm ⁻¹)	E (cm ⁻¹)	E (cm ⁻¹)	E (cm ⁻¹)
2.00	2.910	2.153	3.012	10.065
(Std)	(3.171)	(2.341)	(4.910)	(12.861)
4.00	4.272	4.379	6.305	18.879
5.00	4.348	4.144	7.010	18.458
5.50	4.163	4.008	7.487	21.060
6.00	4.105	4.137	7.385	18.837

Table 2. Oscillator strength values for some specific prominent electronic transitions of f_{JO} values ($\times 10^4$) [Ln(III)-cat] complexes at pH \approx 5.5

Assignment	[Pr ^{III} -cat]							
	1D_2	3P_0	${}^3P_1; {}^1I_6$	3P_2				
E (cm ⁻¹)	16850	20800	21400–21700	22600				
f_{JO}	4.163	4.008	7.487	21.060				
	[Nd ^{III} -cat]							
	${}^1F_{3/2}$	${}^4F_{5/2}; {}^2H_{9/2}$	${}^4H_{7/2}$	${}^4G_{3/2}$	${}^3K_{3/2}$	${}^4D_{3/2}$		
E (cm ⁻¹)	11450	12500; 12600	13500	17300	19000	28300		
f_{JO}	1.494	10.575	10.608	8.016	11.046	11.425		
	[Er ^{III} -cat]							
	${}^4F_{9/2}$	${}^4S_{3/2}$	${}^2H_{11/2}$	${}^4F_{7/2}$	${}^4F_{5/2}$	${}^2G_{9/2}$	${}^4G_{11/2}$	${}^4G_{9/2}$
E (cm ⁻¹)	15300	18400	19200	20500	22200	24600	26400	27400
f_{JO}	7.842	3.830	12.617	8.344	5.286	3.212	16.604	9.887

The oscillator strength values (f_{JO}) composed of τ_λ parameters representing Ln(III)-L interactions. (τ_2) and the symmetry around Ln(III) metal ion (τ_4 , τ_6) are recorded in Table 3. The parameters exhibit a general sequence, $\tau_2 < \tau_4 < \tau_6$, based on their responses towards the Ln(III)-L interactions. The τ_λ parameters are also found to be higher for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} than for Er^{III} which may be expected on account

of higher symmetry produced with the former two due to their larger Ln(III) ion sizes. The τ_2 parameters are, however, smaller than for identical Nd^{III} showing a lesser involvement of covalency for post-Gd metal ions than for pre-Gd metal ions. These observations may be ascertained with the change in IERP-Racah (δE^k) parameters and the nephelauxetic ratio ($\delta E^3/\delta E^1$) values (Table 3). Smaller values of $\delta E^3/\delta E^1$ for Er^{III} than for Nd^{III}, indicate a predominantly ionic pattern of bonding.

Table 3. Values of τ_k parameters δE^3 , δE^1 and $\delta E^3/\delta E^1$ for [Ln(III)-cat] complexes at pH = 5.5

Parameter	Pt ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Er ^{III}
τ_2	-94.65	4.02	3.08
τ_4	11.05	13.31	3.77
τ_6	57.52	11.09	11.51
δE^1	-222.23	21.48	13.86
δE^3	1.03	4.34	2.39
$\delta E^3/\delta E^1$	-0.0046	0.2020	0.1727

The studies reveal that the oscillator values are susceptible towards the Ln(III) environment and their degree of complexation. The trends in τ_2 (smaller than τ_4 and τ_6) and $\delta E^3/\delta E^1$ (negative and smaller) values indicate that the Ln(III)-L interactions in the present case are predominantly ionic.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Ln(III) nitrates (99.99% purity, Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and catechol (Merck, G.R.) were prepared in double-distilled water. HNO₃ (0.1 mol dm⁻³) was used as a reference acid. Carbonate-free NaOH solution (0.2 mol dm⁻³) was used to maintain the pH, which was recorded on an Orion-940 extended ion analyzer system. Measured quantities of alkali were added to adjust the pH

values; variations in concentrations due to addition of alkali was calculated and used in the calculation for the oscillator strength values. The solutions of Ln(III) metal ions blank (0.025 mol dm⁻³) and [Ln(III)-cat] complexes (in 1 : 2 ratio) with total Ln(III) concentration of ≈ 0.025 mol dm⁻³ were prepared and their electronic spectra recorded on a Perkin-Elmer lambda 3B spectrophotometer.

The values of the oscillator strength and Judd-Ofelt parameter were evaluated using Judd-Ofelt⁴ approach. The variations in the inter-electronic repulsion Racah parameters (IERP-Racah) were evaluated using Wong's equations⁵. Pascal compiled self-devised computer software were used to evaluate these spectral parameters using standard equations¹.

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